

POWER UP

The logo consists of the word 'POWER' in a large, bold, sans-serif font. The 'P' is grey, 'O' is orange, 'W' is light green, and 'E' and 'R' are teal. Below 'POWER' is the word 'UP' in a dark blue, bold, sans-serif font. To the right of 'UP' is a graphic illustration of two solar panels on stands, a bright yellow sun with rays, and a row of green arrows pointing downwards.

D8.1 – Communication and dissemination plan

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Executive Summary

This document is the first version of the POWERUP's Communication and Dissemination Plan, which has been developed to spread the knowledge generated during the execution of the project. The plan defines the communication and dissemination strategy, and the related activities. It informs about how, to whom and when project developments and results will be communicated and disseminated, both internally and externally.

POWERUP project is funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe program. The project aims to foster the market uptake of renewable electricity by providing the tools, methodologies, and collaborative frameworks needed to design and implement sustainable, economically viable, and socially accepted energy solutions that contribute to Europe's transition to a sustainable energy future.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
EC	European Commission
ET	Energy Transition
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
PP	Project partner
LRA	Local and Regional Authorities
PA	Public Authority
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
TG	Target Groups
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) is part of the activities of Work Package 8 (WP8) and WP9; specifically, it is the established deliverable for “Task 8.1 – Communication and dissemination plan”, which is implemented during the first half of the project and formally continued under T9.1 in the second half of the project. These tasks centralize most of the coordination and implementation of project’s communication and dissemination activities. WP8 and WP9 consist of several tasks, all of them related to the communication and dissemination of knowledge and information. These are the tasks defined on both WPs:

Table 1 – C&D tasks in WP8 and WP9

WP8	WP9
T8.1 & T9.1 – Communication and dissemination plan	
T8.2 & T9.2 – Communication and dissemination tools	
T8.3 & T9.3 – Deployment of communication and dissemination	
T8.4 – Open Call for Follower Regions	T9.4 – Final POWERUP International Workshop

The POWERUP CDP aims to guarantee the coverage of the project results and achievements, benefits and potential deployment, via the adoption of a large variety of distribution channels. Dissemination and communication activities will be carried out in view of consolidating the project visibility and results. Those activities will be addressed to public authorities, project partners and key stakeholders, besides larger audiences, represented by EU citizens and the public at large.

The CDP addresses:

- A detailed plan of all C&D actions.
- Roles and responsibilities for each C&D action.
- Target audience for each action.
- How to tailor key messages for each target audience.
- Key Performance Indicator (KPI) for each action.

Additionally, as stated at the *Description of the action* of the Grant Agreement, the CDP will be updated twice:

- M12, within WP8.
- M24, in the frame of WP9.

These updates intend to fine-tune the C&D objectives accordingly to the project results achieved and KPIs progress.

2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

A key element of POWERUP project is carrying out activities that increase the impact of its results. To achieve this impact, communication and dissemination activities are designed and timely planned. These activities are focused on promoting actions and results during the whole project duration. As part of the communication strategy, the main elements must be defined: target audience, communication channels and tools, key messages and results monitoring, analysis and evaluation.

Communication activities focus on raising public awareness of the project's objectives and milestones, engaging a broad range of stakeholders. In contrast, dissemination activities are strategically designed to share technical outputs and advancements with specialized audiences—including the scientific community, industry experts, and policymakers—to facilitate knowledge uptake, replication, and further research.

This chapter collects the objectives and principles of the C&D strategy of POWERUP's project.

2.1 Overall objectives

One main objective of this project is to promote the wider uptake of renewable electricity solutions by communication and dissemination activities. There are several Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to this objective, including:

- KPI6: *46 workshops and events for community and stakeholders' engagement.*
- KPI8: *702 public and private stakeholders involved in project activities.*
- KPI9: *372 citizens involved by project activities.*
- KPI14: *50% increase of community acceptance index.*

Communication and dissemination activities have been designed to impact on the different segments of the target audience of the project. The main objectives of these activities are:

- Enabling social engagement activities to improve social acceptance of Renewable Energy Sources (RES).
- Supporting optimal conditions and solutions for the replication and exploitation of the project outcomes.
- Consolidating the project visibility among investors and other RES stakeholders at EU level, to enhance awareness.
- Guaranteeing the scientific and public coverage of the project results.

These objectives are closely related with European "Communication EU research and innovation guidance for project participants" handbook, which highlights the need to communicate the benefits of EU funded projects to the whole society.

2.2 Communication and dissemination principles

The communication activities are grouped in and planned at four levels, according to their communication objectives: pilot territories, supra-regional and national, EU and mainstream. Next, the scope of each level is detailed.

Figure 1 – C&D levels scheme

Pilot territories level

Across the four pilots, local-language campaigns will drive stakeholder engagement and awareness raising of citizens, land-owners, local authorities and local RES stakeholders. By leveraging the project website, social media, and local press, we will communicate key milestones and progress to ensure successful project deployment and buy-in from all regional actors.

Regional and national level

To drive regional or national scale-up, POWERUP will communicate progress and expansion potential to LRA beyond project regions. Using English and local languages, the project website and social media will serve as primary channels to share project progress and news, and engage neighbouring regions and stakeholders.

Replication at EU level

Targeting EU stakeholders, this level pursues maximisation of the replication and exploitation of POWERUP networks. By showcasing pilot achievements in English via social media and the website, we will demonstrate the potential opportunity for other EU regions and the project's contribution to the Energy Transition.

Mainstream level

This level targets a broad EU-wide audience through general channels to communicate project objectives, progress, and results, ensuring maximum visibility across diverse stakeholder groups and the public. It includes all general communication activities and channels.

3 Target audience

POWERUP's communication and dissemination activities are addressed to the target audience of the project. That audience includes all the key stakeholders identified as potential contributors of the project's goals, in terms of increasing the acceptability and market acceptance of new RES projects.

Each of these stakeholders plays a crucial role to improve social acceptance of renewable electricity generation plants. The stakeholders have the potential to make valuable contributions in terms of providing specialized knowledge as well as user experience and acceptance of the proposed tools and business models. Their participation is relevant in co-creation and collaborative activities aligned to the project's mission, among other contributions.

3.1 Priority target groups

The overall success of the POWERUP project relies on the expertise and contributions of the consortium members, as well as on the engagement and participation of the target groups, both within the project pilots, the follower regions and beyond.

Even though target groups have been defined based on several factors, the importance of their implication to the project and their knowledge of the project are the most relevant ones.

Table 2 - Main target groups

Code	Target Group	DESCRIPTION
TG1	Society & citizens	POWERUP will enhance social acceptance of renewable electricity facilities by developing participatory, community-driven business models that integrate social triggers and region-specific needs. This will empower citizens to better engage with energy transition and RES-deployment processes, improving energy literacy and creating a more inclusive decision-making environment.
TG2	Investors & promoters of renewable electricity generation parks	Through the identification of region-specific, socially acceptable business models, investors will be provided with valuable tools and methodologies to develop large-scale RES projects that are economically viable and aligned with local social dynamics. This reduces risk and maximizes project success rates.
TG3	LRAs	LRAs will benefit from tailored guidelines and policy recommendations that support enhanced RES deployment within their regions. These resources will help integrate RES into local development plans while addressing socioeconomic and environmental concerns, fostering sustainable growth and energy transition.

Code	Target Group	DESCRIPTION
TG4	Landowners	Landowners will have access to business models and guidelines for effectively engaging in renewable energy projects. This will enable them to make informed decisions about utilizing their land for RES installations while balancing economic opportunities and environmental sustainability.
TG5	Consultancies & RES industry	Consultancies and industry will be able to leverage the co-created business models, decision support systems, and best practices developed in POWERUP. This will enable them to design, develop, and implement RES projects that are not only technically feasible but also socially acceptable, reducing resistance and fostering long-term success.
TG6	Academia	The open-source tools and methodologies developed by POWERUP will contribute to academic research, advancing knowledge on social acceptance of renewable energy and interdisciplinary approaches to energy transitions. These resources will also support technology transfer activities, leading to potential spin-offs and collaborations between academia and industry.

3.2 Focus strategy for each target groups

To maximise the efficiency of the action, the communication and dissemination activities will be tailored to the different target groups. Specifically, messages and channels will be chosen according to the preferences of each audience. The Table 3 presents the messaging objective and channel used for each target group.

Table 3 - Objectives and channels selected for each target group

Target Group Code	Communication objective	Communication tone	Channel to be used
TG1 Society & citizens	To convey project information. Engagement with project activities addressed to this group.	Clear and direct manner. Not too technical information. More informal.	Web page Social media Press release Surveys and interviews Videos
TG2 Investors & promoters of renewable electricity generation parks	To help to build and maintain long-term trust and credibility relationships with other stakeholders. To ensure an alignment of interests and transparency with other stakeholders' interests. To provide information on project results outcome related to business models and economical results.	Practical information based on results. Formal.	Web page Workshops Press release Newsletter Scientific publications

Target Group Code	Communication objective	Communication tone	Channel to be used
TG3 LRAs	To establish a strategic dialogue that helps to transfer project outcomes into governance. To foster institutional collaboration. To increase the visibility of management practices and encouraging participation in decision-making processes.	Practical information based on results. Formal.	Web page Workshops Press release Newsletter
TG4 Landowners	To convey project information. Engagement with project activities addressed to this group.	Clear and direct manner. Not too technical information. More informal.	Web page Social media Press release Surveys and interviews Videos
TG5 Consultancies & RES industry	To establish a strategic dialogue that helps to transfer project outcomes into practical market action.	Practical information based on results. Formal.	Web page Workshops Press release Newsletter Scientific publications
TG6 Academia	To facilitate an efficient exchange of knowledge and expertise, research and procedures. To enhance learning and foster scientific collaboration	Technically detailed. Formal.	Newsletter Scientific publications

4 Communication, dissemination and engagement channels

4.1 Promotional material

A suite of promotional materials will be developed to address the diverse communication needs of the project. These assets will be designed for use at face-to-face meetings, workshops and conferences, and will also be distributed across the project's digital platforms.

The following materials have been identified as core requirements:

- **Roll-up.** A general-purpose banner in English, outlining the project's objectives, pilot sites, and expected impact. It will serve as a visual centrepiece for stands and on-site events.
- **Printed and digital flyer.** Describing the project's goal, objectives, methodology and expected results, in the five project languages.
- **Project brochure.** A comprehensive document in English highlighting the project approach and its key outputs. It will be used to engage stakeholders once the core developments of the project have been achieved, specifically to facilitate scaling up and replication.

Results from *T8.2 Communication and dissemination tools* include the set of general communication and dissemination material, including the flyer, roll-up and an initial operative version of the webpage (see 4.2). The brochure is part of the results of *T9.2 Communication and dissemination tools*.

4.2 Website page

A dedicated project landing page will be established to facilitate engagement with stakeholders and target audiences. This platform will ensure open and transparent communication regarding the project's progress and milestones. Conceived as a dynamic resource, the website will be continuously updated with a diverse range of content, including news, press releases, original articles, interviews, and relevant external updates.

To guarantee the long-term accessibility of project outputs, the website will be linked to an online repository (e.g., Zenodo), ensuring that public deliverables remain available well beyond the project's operational lifetime. The primary language of the website will be English, with translation options for the regional languages of the pilot sites: Catalan, Greek, Italian, and Portuguese.

In addition to the central landing page, each Project Partner (PP) will feature the project on their institutional websites and/or social media channels. These entries must include, at a minimum:

- **Project Summary:** A brief overview of goals and scope.
- **Visual Identity:** The official project logo.
- **Consortium Details:** A list of participating organizations.
- **Contact Information:** Relevant points of contact for inquiries.
- **Acknowledgment of Funding:** The European flag and the official funding statement.
- **Results:** Key findings and outputs (as they become available).

4.3 Project videos

Promotional videos will serve as high-impact tools to raise public awareness and drive stakeholder engagement. These videos will be designed to communicate the project's objectives, outcomes and innovative solutions in an accessible format, fostering interest and involvement of stakeholders that can benefit from the project.

In collaboration with pilot partners, the project will produce the following audiovisual assets:

- **Project overview videos (2 videos, 100 seconds each):**
 - Phase 1 (WP8, M10). Introductory video presenting the project objectives and expected outcomes.
 - Phase 2 (WP9, M30). A results-oriented video highlighting finalized outcomes and real-world applications.
- **Engagement micro-content (10 videos minimum, 15 seconds each):**
 - A series of high-impact short videos (WP9, M18-M34) designed for social media and digital platforms. Content will include motion graphics, key fact sheets, and testimonials from pilot sites to encourage the uptake of project solutions.

The videos will be produced in English, including subtitles in local languages. They are part of T8.2 and T9.2.

4.4 Social media accounts

Social media will be used as a mainstream communication tool as well as a specific target audience engagement tool. POWERUP will create accounts in different channels to publish specific content.

Although ESTRATS is the main responsible for managing the project's social media accounts, each POWERUP's partner is encouraged to participate in the coverage of the project's progress, with updates published on their own social media channels. By promoting and participating in the different social networks, project partners will support the increasing of reached audience and the overall visibility of the project. Additionally, they must inform ESTRATS regarding the planned events and their development.

The key strategic aspects of POWERUP's social media approach are:

- **Proactive Content Planning:** Generating a communication calendar, to plan the communication content in advance.
- **Consistent Publishing Schedule:** 10 publications per month are expected.
- **Personalized and Impactful Messaging:** Writing in a more personal way and using impactful messages to better engage the general public and each stakeholder.
- **High-Quality Visual Content:** Using interesting and good quality pictures to ensure content is suitable for different channels.

The objective in terms of engagement with social media throughout the lifetime of the project is a cumulative total of at least **500 followers** across all platforms. To do so, and to ensure constant engagement, the project plans an average of **10 publications per month** across all platforms.

4.4.1 LinkedIn

POWERUP will leverage LinkedIn audience targeting capabilities, to optimise stakeholders' engagement. Based on professional roles and geographical locations, posts will be tailored to specific interests and needs of each stakeholder group.

Concise and focused information about the project activities, news or outcomes will be regularly published. Additionally, longer articles will be published to highlight specific project results during the second half of the project.

LinkedIn handle: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/powerup-horizon>

4.4.2 Youtube

Youtube will serve as the project's primary visual repository, hosting all the videos listed in section 4.3. This platform will facilitate stakeholders and the general public to get an overview of the project's main objectives and achievements. The channel will also host recordings of public project webinars and workshops. This ensures that high-value technical content remains accessible to those unable to attend live sessions.

The dedicated Youtube channel can be accessed at: <https://www.youtube.com/@powerup-horizon>

4.4.3 Instagram

Instagram will be utilized as a primary platform for visual storytelling, leveraging high-impact imagery and short-form video content to maximize reach. It will therefore be used to relay information about specific project events (e.g. project meetings) and to drive engagement through compelling visual content.

The dedicated Instagram profile can be accessed at: https://www.instagram.com/powerup_horizon/

4.5 Press releases and newsletters

The publication of high-quality press coverage is highly beneficial to increase the long-term visibility, keep interested parties informed of project progress and leave a lasting impact to parties curious about the project. The project will produce **at least 12 press releases** throughout the project lifetime, predominantly published when milestones or high interest outcomes are reached. They will be written in English and distributed to a wide EU audience through their addition to the project website and publication on social media channels. Additionally, PPs will be invited to share the press release through their own web site and social media channel. They will also be submitted to the Horizon Europe Communication Team for potential dissemination through Horizon channels, such as the Horizon Magazine.

POWERUP **will also publish 6 newsletters** in English, following a regular interval of 6 months. Each one will serve the purpose of providing a summary of the most relevant news from the previous period, as

well as any update from PPs. These newsletters will be distributed to web registered users and will also be available through the project website and on the LinkedIn channel. Furthermore, PPs will be encouraged to include the newsletters in their own communications channels to maximize reach.

4.6 Workshops and events

Workshops and events are planned to engage stakeholders and citizens. The project aims to achieve the involvement of more than 700 public and private stakeholders and 370 citizens, through different activities, such as interviews, surveys, focus group, workshop and webinars. These activities will take place in different phases of the project: identification of triggers and requirements (WP3), co-creation of business models and tools (WP4), and validation of results (WP6).

4.6.1 Workshops and webinars

POWERUP will organize **at least 46 workshops and webinars** to foster community and stakeholders' engagement. The distribution and typology of these events are as follows:

- 12 tool design workshops (WP4): 3 per pilot region.
- 20 validation workshops (WP6): 5 per pilot region.
- 12 engagement webinars (WP6): 3 per pilot region.
- 2 replication workshops for follower regions (WP7).

The expected audience, considering all workshops and webinars, is around 460 attendants.

4.6.2 Individual feedback inputs

Individual feedback inputs will be collected from the defined activities:

- Interviews: 32 stakeholders participating, an average of 8 per pilot region.
- Surveys: 100 participants, an average of 25 per pilot region).
- Focus groups: 100 participants, an average of 25 per pilot region).

4.7 Public events and clustering

4.7.1 Participation in public events and conferences

Representatives of the POWERUP project partners will present the project in **at least 7 national or international conferences or events** relevant to the challenges facing renewable energy project uptake. The aim is to build synergies, share project outcomes, enlarge the dissemination reach and interest in the project and promote the growth of the community in of the POWERUP digital hub.

The specific conferences and projects to be attended shall be defined before M6. Once they are listed, the attendance should be planned and shared to the project partners.

4.7.2 Clustering with projects

Networking with other EU funded projects can be highly beneficial in increasing the reach and visibility of the project. POWERUP will promote clustering with **at least 10 other relevant projects**, to leverage synergies and foster cooperation.

POWERUP will identify **at least 5 similar projects** and initiatives to cluster with. Upon invitation from CINEA, the project will contribute to common information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between Horizon Europe supported actions. The specific cluster activities will be defined in WP9.

4.7.3 Open Call for Follower Regions

The POWERUP replicability strategy is built upon the engagement of at least 10 Follower Regions, which will be identified through a transparent Open Call and a rigorous selection procedure. This initiative is designed to ensure that project solutions are adopted by the most suitable regional candidates. The selection criteria should prioritise follower regions aligned with the "Acceleration Areas" and at least 2 follower regions in Third Countries to foster collaboration with new markets.

4.8 Scientific publications

The work produced during the POWERUP project will be used to publish at least 3 scientific papers focusing on aspects such as the projects key results, main lessons learnt, or recommendations for the future.

5 Monitoring

5.1 What to monitor

The monitoring of POWERUP project implies a systematic tracking, reviewing and reporting of the progress towards the defined targets. In a CDP, several key factors will be closely monitored: the number and type of publications, the number and type of activities, and the audience reached by each channel. Quantitative parameters can be used to measure that impact, nonetheless, quantitative parameters must be used to consider the reactions generated by the project and the level of satisfaction of the audience.

Monitoring activities will be based on a continuous improvement process.

Figure 2 - Principles of monitoring and evaluation, based on continuous improvement

5.2 Communication and dissemination KPIs

Key Performance Indicators are the quantifiable metrics used to measure the progress of the C&D Plan, with regards to its specific strategic goals. The following table includes the indicators defined by POWERUP for monitoring and evaluation of the different communication and dissemination activities. The related KPIs are the objectives set to be achieved at the end of the project (M36).

Table 4 - Communication and dissemination activities KPIs

Tool	Indicator	Count (end of project)
Social media	# followers	500
	# average publications per month	10
	# of reach / impressions / interactions	10.000+
Videos	# 15'' videos	10
	# 100'' video	2
	# views / reach (all videos combined)	4.000+
Newsletter	# publications	6
Press release	# publications	12
Publications	# scientific publications	3
Conference & events	# participated events	7
	# attendees	200+
Networking	# clustering with similar projects	10

6 Dissemination of results and open access

POWERUP results must be disseminated by each beneficiary as soon as possible. They must be disclosed to the public by the appropriate means. The obligation of disclosing results doesn't limit the security and confidentiality responsibilities, neither the obligation to protect results or personal data.

Results dissemination planned by a beneficiary requires a 15-day advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results to be disseminated.

Open access provides online access to scientific information free of charge to the user and reusable. Open accessible results go hand in hand with more efficient science and enhances innovation in public and private sectors. The Commission has made open access mandatory for all Horizon projects.

Annex I: Chronogram

More information: www.powerup-horizon.eu

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